

Cruise Report: Cascadia H.O.P.S. 2020

R/V Oceanus: OC2006A
Oregon Seagoing Research Vessel Program
NSF MARSSAM Engineering
July 7-13, 2020
Newport, Oregon

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Executive Summary

Cascadia High-Resolution Observations of Paleo Systems (H.O.P.S.) was a 7-day expedition of R/V Oceanus along the Oregon and Washington continental slope that included scientists from Oregon State University, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, University of Oregon, and Western Washington University. Support for the expedition came from the Oregon Oceangoing Research Vessel Program and from the National Science Foundation. Our primary goal was to identify and sample sedimentary deposits suitable for study of the environmental, oceanographic, ice sheet, tectonic, and geomagnetic histories of the Pacific Northwest. While collecting these samples, we also conducted experiments to test gravity and piston coring technology, including the difference between galvanized steel core barrels with and without thin film ceramic coating, as well as instrumenting the jumbo piston coring system with accelerometers to iteratively reduce coring artifacts. Shipboard data collected includes CHIRP sub-bottom survey data, multi-sensor core logging data, and sediment pore-water pH. Cores will be split and described at the Oregon State University Marine and Geology Repository following the expedition.

As one of the first cruises to be implemented following the University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS) stand down in response to global COVID-19 pandemic, this expedition had to implement several additional safety protocols to protect the health of the crew and scientists. In addition, we had to limit shipboard participation, although we worked closely with Oregon State University Ship Operations to develop and test methods of remote involvement for students and shore-based scientists.

Four sedimentary deposits, likely spanning the Last Glacial Maximum to Holocene based on radiocarbon dating of equivalent units sampled during prior cruise OC1706B (see [Affiliations with Other Expeditions and Programs](#)), were sampled on the upper slope, at stations around 835 m water depth north and south of the Astoria Canyon offshore Oregon, between 630 and 730 m water depth north of Grays Canyon, and around 900 m water depth north of Quinault Canyon offshore Washington. Two sedimentary deposits were sampled from syncline basins on the lower slope offshore Oregon in depths of about 1975 and 2100 m that have unknown ages likely extending to pre-Holocene times. A final deposit was sampled on the upper Astoria Fan around 2200 m water depth to try and re-core a deposit cored in 1965 and described to have sediments containing ice rafted debris. A total of 9 Jumbo Piston Cores, 6 Gravity Cores, 7 Multi Cores, 6 flow-through water samples, and 4 plankton net tow samples were taken.

Science Team

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Introduction

Cascadia H.O.P.S. 2020 was a 7-day cruise of R/V Oceanus, OC2006A, primarily focused on sampling seafloor sediments from the Oregon and Washington margin continental slopes with multi-cores, gravity cores, and piston cores. Sediment targets were primarily from locations that would likely have minimal influence from erosive turbidites and may be suitable for paleo- oceanographic, environmental, and magnetic purposes. Coring locations focused on upper slope deposits (~600-900 m) from near the Astoria Canyon off Oregon to near the Quinault Canyon off Washington, two basins on the lower slope basins (~1950-2100 m) on the Oregon Margin, and a site on the upper Astoria Fan (~2200 m). Engineering tests were conducted by taking parallel gravity cores and jumbo piston cores (JPC) from three locations to test differences between galvanized steel core barrels and core barrels painted with Cerakote Elite thin film ceramic coating. All JPC casts were also instrumented with accelerometers both at the piston core weight stand as well as on the trigger arm to allow for assessment of the relative motion of the piston and trigger corer with the goal to reduce deformation of recovered sediments during the coring process.

Scientific Motivation

Over eight million people live within the Columbia River watershed and Oregon's coastal communities and are dependent on the region's water, ecosystem, and other natural resources. Anthropogenic climate change is projected to increase annual air temperatures, increase winter precipitation, and decrease summer precipitation in the Columbia River watershed over the next century; however, there is still uncertainty and disagreement in global climate models over the magnitude and even sign of these changes—particularly for precipitation (Rupp et al., 2017). Geologic archives offer a means to study how regional climate has evolved under a variety of natural forcing (e.g. due to changes in Earth's orbit and/or changes in atmospheric CO₂ concentrations), which in turn can be used to assess the performance of global climate models or, in some cases, serve as analogs for projected anthropogenic climate change.

From the early to late Holocene (~11 thousand years ago to present), the Northern Hemisphere transitioned from receiving less (more) radiative energy from the sun during the summer (winter) because of changes in Earth's orbit. This provides a natural laboratory to study climate variability under different boundary conditions, with modeled middle Holocene regional temperature (~6 thousand years ago) of around 2 °C warmer than preindustrial (Braconnot et al., 2007) about equivalent to projected anthropogenic warming for 2050 under moderate (RCP 4.5) CO₂ emissions scenarios (Rupp et al., 2017). Reconstructions of Columbia River discharge through this time will inform on integrated watershed precipitation and snowpack, while study of benthic oxygenation will help reconstruct the temporal, spatial, and depth range extents of hypoxic events on the margin.

The Cordilleran Ice Sheet covered much of Western North America from Washington to Alaska during the last ice age. During warming associated with the last deglaciation, ice dammed lakes were released in a series of floods (some of which are known as the Missoula Floods) through the Columbia River. Freshwater from these and other freshwater discharges entered the North Pacific, with high amplitude signals detectable in marine sediment cores to the south at the Southern Oregon margin (Lopes & Mix, 2009). Proposed coring locations are chosen to map out the distribution of sediments associated with these floods on the Oregon continental slope, from sites proximal and distal to the Astoria Canyon. Geochemical and magnetic fingerprinting of potential terrestrial source region sediments will be used to investigate how sediment and floodwater sources may have evolved through the last ice age and deglaciation, providing new insight to the dynamics of the southern margin of the Cordilleran Ice Sheet. Insight to the Cordilleran Ice Sheet dynamics can in turn be used as a comparative study to present and projected dynamics of the currently deglaciating Greenland Ice Sheet.

In addition, offshore geologic records of turbidites are a critical component in determining the size and recurrence intervals of earthquakes on the Cascadia Subduction Zone, and consequently the seismic hazard for the coastal Pacific Northwest regions (Frankel et al., 2015; Goldfinger et al., 2012). Some of the sediment cores collected during this cruise targeted shallow sediments at the canyon heads along the margin, which may fail during shaking and serve as the source of gravity flows and the region's turbidite record. These cores will be used to determine the shear strength of the shallow sediments, to combine with ground-motions from numerical simulations of earthquakes in assessing a range of possible earthquake types, sizes, and locations that could produce the margin's turbidite record.

Key Scientific Questions

- What was the environment and climate of the Pacific Northwest in the past, when orbital forcing produced climate changes similar to the greenhouse gas forcing of today? What does this tell us about the future of precipitation and snowpack in our warming world?
- What is the history of ocean hypoxia and anoxia of the Cascadia Margin, particularly during the early Holocene and past warm times? By studying modern diagenetic processes, can we develop proxies to quantitatively assess past oxygen concentrations?
- What is the history of freshwater discharge to the Northeast Pacific from the Columbia River and other outlets influenced by the southern margin of the Cordilleran Ice Sheet prior to the last glacial maximum?
- What is the nature of previously described 'ice-rafted debris' deposits on the Oregon Margin? What is the stratigraphic context for these deposits and what are their ages?
- What is the rate of retreat of the Cordilleran out of the Columbia River drainage basin once the ice sheet destabilized at the end of the last ice age? How did the rate and timing of retreat compare between the southeastern (continental) and southwestern (marine) margins?
- Can the marine record be used to study the late Pleistocene to Holocene centennial to millennial variations of the geomagnetic field? How does this record compare with lacustrine records throughout western North America?
- Is it possible based on sediment strength to quantify the level of shaking, and thus earthquake magnitude, types, and locations, necessary to cause canyon head sediments to fail and produce our turbidite record?

COVID-19 Safety Precautions

On March 17, 2020 the University-National Oceanographic Laboratory System (UNOLS) announced a 30 day stand down of the US academic fleet as a response to the global COVID-19 pandemic, which was ultimately extended to July 1st. This impacted the initial scheduled dates for the Cascadia H.O.P.S. 2020 coring cruise in June 2020. As one of the first cruises to be rescheduled and implement following the stand down, extra precautions were taken on OC2006A to ensure the cruise could be executed safely and responsibly. These included a reduced science party size and limited student involvement in shipboard activities.

Prior to the cruise, members of the science party completed 14 days of self-isolation in their homes and underwent two rounds of COVID-19 testing. During this period, scientists conducted at home self-monitoring, including tracking possible symptoms and logging morning/evening body temperatures, through an online Discovery Health portal. Scientists arrived at the ship on July 6th for mobilization and were not allowed to leave again until the cruise was over.

During the cruise, several safety protocols were in place, developed in collaboration with the R/V Oceanus' Captain, Oregon State University Marine Operations, and Chief Scientists. Facial coverings were required in public spaces on this ship, except while eating and when safety or communication (e.g. outside during coring operations) were a factor. Many areas of this ship, such as the bridge, galley, and engineering spaces, were considered restricted spaces. Mealtimes were modified and extra precautions were taken in the galley and mess to allow physical distancing and prevent transmission.

Should anyone on the ship display symptoms, a cabin was left unoccupied to be an isolation room and a likely diagnosis would be determined remotely by George Washington Medical. If the diagnosis indicated a likely COVID-19 case, RV Oceanus would immediately return to port and proceed under the direction of the Coast Guard Port Captain.

No members of the scientific party or crew displayed symptoms during the cruise. Information given to OC2006A participants regarding COVID-19 safety precautions is provided in Appendix 1: COVID19 Safety Information.

Education and Remote Participation

While the initial proposal for Cascadia H.O.P.S. included educating students in marine geology methods as a primary objective, we were asked by Ship Operations to limit student involvement as a safety measure related to the global COVID-19 pandemic. Accordingly, only one upper-level graduate student, Deepa Dwyer, sailed. However, before the UNOLS stand down we had already recruited three research experience for undergraduate (REU) students and one new master's student to sail and participate in post-cruise research. In an effort to keep these students involved in sample collection, we developed ways to involve these students and others remotely in the expedition.

We developed a website¹ to act as an outreach hub that we could use to share information, links, and blog posts for remote participants. This site included links to live readouts of shipboard instruments, including the sub-bottom profiler, and cameras to view deck operations. To involve the remote participants in our discussions and provide a platform for remote participants to engage and ask questions, we established a chatroom through Google Chat. Daily audio conference calls were held through Zoom at 1215 hours to recap the preceding and upcoming 24 hours of operations.

For the most part the daily conference calls and Google Chat were helpful and most of the remote participants engaged at some point, either by asking questions, contributing to discussions about coring/surveying, or listening into one of the daily conference calls. On July 10, we had internet connection issues and could not execute the conference call or Google Chat in the early afternoon. Other than this instance and a few second delay in the conference call audio, the ship to shore communication was successful.

¹ <http://paleomag.ceoas.oregonstate.edu/hops/>

Affiliations with Other Expeditions and Programs

Cascadia H.O.P.S. was supported by the Oregon Seagoing Research Vessel Program, a state-funded program that “provides ship days to students and researchers from all of Oregon’s public universities and natural resource agencies for the use of RV Oceanus to explore key coastal issues, including climate change impacts, ocean acidification and renewable energy.”² The cruise builds on the previously successful Oregon Seagoing Research Vessel Program proposal, “An environmental history of the Columbia River” and the resulting June 2017 cruise, OC1706B³, which recovered 5 jumbo piston cores, 3 gravity cores, 3 multi-cores, and sub-bottom acoustic data. OC1706B included the marine geology training of a number of undergraduate to graduate students, with results presented by students at scientific conferences (Churchill et al., 2017; Lavoie et al., 2018; Robles et al., 2018; Romo et al., 2017) and forming the basis for an undergraduate thesis (Valdez-Hernandez, 2020).

Sites identified and cored during OC1706B were transformative in demonstrating the potential for understanding the paleoenvironmental history of the Pacific Northwest and Northeast Pacific using previously understudied sedimentary deposits in isolated basins on the Oregon Margin continental slope. These initial observations helped support OC2006A scientists, Reilly and Walczak, to plan and participate in the multichannel seismic surveys of these deposits during the September–October 2017 UNOLS Early Career Researcher Chief Scientist Training Cruise, RR1718. Data from both cruises are currently being used to support an IODP proposal to collect new long drill cores from the region. A pre-proposal⁴ received favorable reviews and encouragement to develop a full proposal, which material and data collected during OC2006A will support.

In addition to the scientific goals of this cruise, our secondary objective was to perform engineering trials for the National Science Foundation Marine Sediment Sampling (MARSSAM) Group, of which co-Chief Walczak is PI. Systems to be tested included the addition of orientation/acceleration sensors to the Jumbo Piston Coring equipment to reduce coring artifacts on sediment recovery and evaluating the advantages and drawbacks of ceramic coatings applied to JPC barrels in reducing pullout friction and hence wire tension. The National Science Foundation provided two additional days of ship time and supported coring technician participation on the cruise for this purpose.

Schedule

OC2006A started aboard RV Oceanus in Newport, Oregon on July 7, 2020 and ended in the same location on July 13, 2020. A mobilization day was held on July 6, 2020 and a demobilization day was held on July 14, 2020.

² <https://ceoas.oregonstate.edu/research/oceangoing/>

³ <http://ceoas.oregonstate.edu/features/sealegs/>

⁴ https://docs.iodp.org/Proposal_Cover_Sheets/963-Pre_Walczak_cover.pdf

Science Summary

CHIRP Survey

The 3.5 kHz sub-bottom profiler uses Compressed High Intensity Radar Pulses (CHIRP) for sub-bottom profiling of the upper sediment layers of the ocean. The transmitter is a Knudsen Engineering model 3260 using an Edgetech 3300 conical beam transducer array. During surveys, we typically used frequencies between 3.5 and 5 kHz, and varied transducer power, and pulse length to improve penetration and resolution, and best image the sedimentary structures of interest.

Sediment Coring

Sediment Coring Operations

Sediment coring operations were led by the Oregon State University MARSSAM group,⁵ and focused on the collection of multi-cores (MC-400), gravity cores, and jumbo piston cores. At Station 1, a 10' trigger weight corer set-up was used independently of the jumbo piston corer as a gravity corer to recover the upper 2 m with as little coring deformation as possible. All other gravity cores were taken using the MARSSAM 20' Giant Gravity Coring set-up, which uses the piston core weights and two lengths of 10' core pipe. Piston cores were rigged using three (30'), four (40'), or five (50') core pipes, depending on survey data, expected pull-out tension, and conversations with the ship's captain, crew, and marine technicians. A 10' trigger core was collected with each piston core deployment. A GoPro camera and

⁵ <http://marssam.ceoas.oregonstate.edu/>

light in pressure casing was attached to some of the multi-cores collected at depths shallower than 1500 m to collect video of their deployments.

All cores were sectioned into up to 150 cm long sections, labeled with cruise ID, core number, section number, and archive/working halves. A continuous paleomagnetic line was drawn on the archive halves, so that when split all sections will be oriented relative to each other. Cores will be split in to archive and working halves and described at the Oregon State University Marine and Geology Repository (OSU MGR)⁶ after the cruise, excluding Core OC2006A-2GC, which was consumed in entirety for pore water analysis.

Multi Sensor Core Logger (MSCL)

A Geotek Multi Sensor Core Logger (MSCL), housed in a seagoing laboratory van, provided a means for the shipboard logging of physical properties data from recovered core samples. This instrument collected magnetic susceptibility, gamma ray attenuation, resistivity, and p-wave velocity data. As is typical for the Oregon State University MCSL system, gamma ray attenuation data was calibrated against an aluminum standard to estimate bulk sediment density and resistivity data were calibrated against water samples with varying salinity. Typically, cores were given time to equilibrate with ambient temperature before being run, run at 1 cm resolution, and with 5 second averaging time for all sensors. However, Core OC2006A-2GC was run immediately after recovery at 2 cm resolution so that it could be quickly processed for porewater geochemistry without warming up first. Our data suggest that the magnetic susceptibility data for this core likely experienced some drift as the cold core was passed through the sensor.

⁶ <http://www.osu-mgr.org>

MARSSAM Engineering Tests

At every JPC station, Star-Oddi accelerometer and tilt sensors were bolted to the jumbo piston core weight stand and trigger core arm to collect data on the relative motion of the trigger and jumbo piston corer. Following the cruise this data will be processed following the methods of Bourillet et al. (2007) in an effort to refine the calculations of piston scope and trigger line length used in rigging the corer to reduce coring deformation of the stratigraphic record. These findings will be vetted via evaluation of the contemporaneous MSCL data. In addition, we trialed the use of Cerakote Elite thin film ceramic coating applied to the exterior of our galvanized steel barrels on sediment penetration, pullout friction, and core recovery. Three sites of varying lithologies at Stations 1, 6, and 7 were cored with identical conditions, once with the standard galvanized barrels and again with the Cerakote barrels.

Pore Water Geochemistry

We reoccupied the location of Core OC1706B-11JC to investigate downcore changes in pore water geochemistry and how those changes relate to magnetic mineral assemblages, solid geochemistry changes, organic biomarkers, and microbiology. Cores OC2006A-2GC and 4MC were taken using a 10ft gravity core and the MC-400, respectively, and whole round samples were taken for pore water analysis, organic biomarkers, and microbiology. This sampling consumed the entire cores. Core OC2006A-3GC was taken soon after Core OC2006A-2GC and will be split, described, and archived for additional sampling and analysis to compare with the pore water data. A correlation can be made using the MSCL logging data.

Core OC2006A-2GC was sectioned to test three different pore water sampling techniques: centrifugation, squeezing and rhyzons. Pore water was kept from each for trace metals, and remaining water was alternatively kept for testing anions, DOC and pH. The water for trace metals was extracted and filtered at 0.45um and acidified with ultra pure 6M HCl. Samples for anions, DOC and pH were also filtered at 0.45um; anions kept in non-acid washed plastic vial, and DOC in glass. pH was measured on

board the ship as quickly as the water was extracted. The inevitable warming and processing time means that the pH data is likely not entirely accurate, but very useful for general interpretations. A sub sampling of pristine sediment was taken between these sections for microbial/DNA analyses. These samples were kept in sterilized bags at -80°C. The residual sediment from samples processed for pore water extraction was kept in a freezer for later analyses.

At the same site, core OC2006A-4MC was deployed to better capture the sediment water interface. All multicore sediment was sampled using centrifugation, with sediment sectioned under a nitrogen atmosphere in a glove bag. Pore water from the first tube was used for trace metal and anions (filtered and acidified as above). Pore water from the second tube was used for DOC and pH (again as above). Pore water from a third tube was sampled two days post recovery for trace metal and anions, as a test for the stability of the geochemistry when stored in a cold van. Samples for microbial/DNA analyses (as above) were taken from the third tube sampled.

Plankton Net Tows and Water Samples

Surface plankton net tows and water samples were collected at most stations. Plankton net tows were collected from 5 m water depth using a 150 μ m mesh tow net and will be used to evaluate microplankton species and abundance in the water column overlying the sites for comparison to the multi-core surface sediments. Collected specimens were transferred to glass ball jars and fixed within 10 minutes of recovery in ~10% ethanol, following which they were kept refrigerated. Surface water samples for stable isotope analysis were collected from the wet lab seawater intake within 5 minutes of departing the same station. Bottom water samples were collected from the clear water above the sediment-water interface in recovered multi-core tubes immediately upon recovery.

Station Summaries

Station 0: Opportunity Net Tow and Water Sample

Early in the afternoon of July 7th R/V Oceanus had an engine issue which required powering down for several hours. This occurred when we were over the upper continental slope in an unusually warm water mass, so we elected to collect a net tow and water sample.

Station 1: Reoccupation of OC1706B-11JC/Pore Water/MARSSAM Engineering Test

Core OC1706B-11JC was the final piston core recovered during previous cruise OC1706B near Core OC1706B-6JC. The sedimentary deposit was later surveyed with four crossing lines during RR1718, identifying a thick sedimentary sequence that appears to be a good target for scientific drilling. Core OC1706B-11JC has received a considerable amount of attention since recovery, with radiocarbon, XRF geochemistry, CT scans, radiogenic sediment provenance, micropaleontological, diatom speciation and stable isotope data collection in progress.

One aspect of 11JC that is particularly intriguing is sedimentological evidence for past changes in redox conditions. To better understand these past changes in the context of modern biogeochemical processes, we collected two short gravity cores, OC2006A-2GC (201 m) and 3GC (206 m), and a multicore, OC2006A-4MC overnight July 6th into July 7th from pre-cruise station HOPS20-05. OC2006A-2GC was logged on the MSCL within minutes of being sectioned on the deck after recovery and then whole round samples were taken for pore water geochemistry, consuming all sediment recovered. The paired gravity core, OC2006A-3GC, was recovered from the same location and will be available for sampling after it is split into working and archive halves. The two cores can be correlated using the MSCL data, although sensor drift may be an issue for OC2006A-2GC, which was run before equilibrating to ambient temperature. Water sample OC2006A-5W was taken from the flow through system as we were leaving this station.

We returned to Station 1 on July 12th as an alternate site for the MARSSAM engineering core barrel test, after an initial attempt at Station 5 was compromised from burying the bomb (piston core weight) in the sediment. During Cruise OC1706B, Core 11JC reached pull out tensions around 18,000 lbs using normal

unpainted galvanized steel barrels. Core OC2006A-27JC, cored using the Cerakote Elite painted barrels had a maximum pull out tension of 14,037 and recovered 10.03 m of sediments, although with a void between the lowermost sections 7 and 8. Plankton net tow sample OC2006A-28NT and water sample OC2006A-29W were taken from this station following coring operations.

Station 2: Upper Slope North Astoria Canyon Site

The pre-cruise site HOPS20-06 was selected in the hopes of finding a sedimentary deposit that could be compared to OC1706B-11JC at similar water depth on the upper slope and North of the Astoria Canyon. We visited this area on July 7th. We began by taking a multi-core sample, OC2006A-6MC, on the upper slope near the Astoria Canyon head to characterize the shear strength and porosity of surface sediments that could be mobilized into the canyon during shaking.

While surveying for a site suitable for paleoclimate study using the CHIRP system, we observed a thick transparent unit that draped the underlying topography and approached 10 m in thickness at some locations around 840 m water depth. The underlying topography was characterized by a hard reflector that appears to represent an erosional surface and influences the visible bathymetry. We chose to target this transparent unit with a multi core, OC2006A-7MC, a 20 ft giant gravity core, OC2006A-9GC (4.35 m), and a 30 ft piston core OC2006A-10JC (6.12 m). The piston core over penetrated, with about 10 cm of mud visible on top of the weights as it landed. However, it seems that, based on MSCL data, a composite record of the complete stratigraphy can be developed using the overlap between Core OC2006A-9GC and 10PC. Core OC2006A-10JC appears to have bottomed out in a high-density unit-likely the hard reflector in the CHIRP data created by the erosional surface.

Station 3: Upper Slope North Quinault Canyon Site

A principle goal of this cruise was to collect cores suitable for paleoceanographic study of the major southwestern drainages of the Cordilleran ice sheet, including the Juan de Fuca and Puget Lobe. In preliminary site selection an effort was made to identify possible sites with low-energy accumulation of Holocene sediments (i.e. avoiding erosive turbidites) and an expanded deglacial stratigraphic record. Station 3 on the upper Continental slope north of Quinault canyon was located in on the back side of a small drape just south of a paleo drainage of the Juan de Fuca lobe occupied by in present day by the Sol Duc river. This drainage, long since abandoned, formed a shelf-crossing canyon at LGM. The site location is separated from this conduit by a small rise, which should have provided protection from erosive currents, while allowing proximity for sensitive recording of Juan de Fuca drainage.

On July 8th, our initial survey began at the preliminary target HOPS20-09, around 600-700 m water depth, located just north of Quinault Canyon. It was difficult to image deep into the sediment with the CHIRP system, there was no transparent sediment drape, and the sub-bottom data contained several hard reflectors. Accordingly, we abandoned this location and transited to our alternate site, HOPS20-10, and completed a survey starting slightly deeper than 900 m water depth to shallower bathymetry. Here we observed a thick continuous transparent drape that thickened from about 5 m around 900 m water depth to 10 m around 800 m water depth. We selected a site near 900 m to capture what we interpreted to be the deglacial sequence, although future cruises may want to target the expanded transparent unit around 830 m. As this was 'terra incognita' for our coring group, the first jumbo piston core was rigged to 30' (OC2006A-11JC/TC), which came back with a pullout of 12,800 lbs and 8.17 m of recovery with a 2.51 m trigger core. Based on this success, a 40' jumbo piston corer was rigged (OC2006A-12JC/TC), coming back with a pullout of 15,000 lbs and 11.17 m of recovery, with a 2.29 m trigger core. MSCL data indicates overlap between the trigger and piston cores allowed for complete recovery of the stratigraphic section. We finished occupation with an MC-400 (OC2006A-13MC), recovering 3 full cores between 0.36 – 0.38 m in length. The MC-400 was sampled for bottom water stable isotopes.

On our return south we stopped to deploy a multi-corer to sample the failing surface in ~660 m water depth at one of the dendritic heads of Quinault Canyon (OC2006A-14MC). Four multi-cores were recovered of between 0.04 – 0.085 m in length, showing a clear discontinuity between gray (presumably Pleistocene) clay and a few cm of green/brown Holocene sediment. The hope is this core will inform on the physical strength of materials that fail during seismic events in the Cascadia subduction zone, and provide a source of sediment for the turbidites that support our regional paleoseismic record.

Station 4: Upper Slope North Gray's Canyon Site

During the overnight transit to Station 3 (HOPS20-09 and 10), we directed the ship to survey over a broad rise perched on the upper slope immediately south of the Grays Canyon system. Grays Canyon formed the primary conduit for drainage to the ocean of the Puget Lobe of the Cordilleran Ice sheet, as well as the series of proglacial lakes (including Glacial Lake Russell) that occupied the southern margin of the trough as the ice sheet retreated to the north at the end of the Last Glacial Maximum. The Chirp sub-bottom profile revealed an expanded (~10 m) surface expression of a transparent presumably Holocene drape on the North shoulder of a broad, shallow channel transiting the rise (Unit H). As we transited north perpendicular to the rise, this unit thinned and eventually pinched out, exposing an underlying unit of intermediate transparency and with some visible structure (Unit D). Continuing north, Unit D also thinned, exposing an underlying hard reflector similar in character to expression of LGM sediments imaged and sampled during precursor cruise OC1706B (Unit G). We elected to return to this location as a 'site of opportunity' on July 9th in place of the pre-cruise location HOPS20-08 to collect an offset series of three piston and gravity cores, with the goal to collect an expanded LGM-Holocene stratigraphic sequence. Overnight before coring operations began, we completed a second Chirp survey to fine-tune site selection.

We began the transect at the outcropping of the hardest reflector imaged (Unit G), collecting a 20' giant gravity core in ~640 m water depth. This core came back with a pullout of 7500 lbs and 3.57 m sediment recovery. At the next site along the transect, where the unit thinned and we could access more of Unit

D, we rigged a 30' piston core, OC2006A-16JC/TC, recovering 8.07 m of sediment with pull out tension of 9,500 lbs. This piston core clearly over penetrated and there was at least 5 cm of mud on top of the piston core weights. With the low pull out tension and easy penetration of this piston core, we decided to rig a 50' piston core, the longest piston core ever rigged to our knowledge on R/V Oceanus, for the final location along our transect targeting the most expanded sequence of Unit H and D surveyed. OC2006A-18JC was successful, recovering 14.04 m of sediment with pull out tensions of only 11,907 lbs. At Station 4, we also took a water sample, OC2006A-17W, and plankton net tow sample, OC2006A-19NT.

Station 5: Lower Slope Basin (MHH) Site

Pre-cruise location HOPS20-03 is in a small enclosed syncline basin on the lower slope with ponded sediments previously surveyed with a CHIRP system during Cruise OC1706B and with a high-resolution multi-channel seismic system during Cruise RR1718. During Cruise OC1706B, we first noticed that we could image more than 50 m of sediment using the CHIRP system with structure that seemed to have hemipelagic sediments with no hard reflectors. During cruise RR1718, we shot crossing lines and noted a thick sedimentary sequence that has likely evolved as the basin has evolved tectonically. Our goal was to collect a core to characterize the deposit and assess if this would be a good target for scientific drilling.

We chose a core site at the Cruise RR1718 crossing lines and rigged a multi-core and a 40 ft piston core, OC2006A-23JC. The multi-core recovered four cores with slightly cloudy water on top, that settled to clear water in a few hours. Two cores were archived, and one was sectioned at 2 cm intervals. The piston core had a maximum pull out tension of 10,377 lbs and recovered 11.11 m. Both the trigger core and piston core likely over penetrated the sediments, with about 5 cm of mud on top of the piston core weight and mud on top of the trigger core. We recommend re-coring this site with a longer piston core

in a future expedition. The core catcher contained green mud, while gray and green mud were present at section breaks. Water sample OC2006A-24W was taken from the flow-through seawater while leaving this station.

Station 6: Upper Astoria Fan Site/MARSSAM Engineering Test

In 1965 a cruise aboard the R/V Yaquina (Y6501) cored site 'E2', nominally at 45° 43.32' N 125° 37.02' W and 2319 m water depth. Core descriptions indicate the recovered core contained 0.8 m of fine, presumably Holocene, silt and clay overlying glacial sediments with clasts of ice-rafted debris up to several cm in diameter hosted in a fine clay matrix. Clast lithologies were diverse, including andesite presumably sourced east of the Cascade mountains. These findings are remarkable as we have yet to identify similar lithologies in the late glacial/deglacial sites cored during OC1706B or OC2006A, and unfortunately little of the original core remains in the OSU MGR. We endeavored reoccupation of this legacy site, in the hopes that we would be able to recover similar sediments for study of IRD provenance (potentially useful for calibrating geochemical provenance of the fine-grained fraction recovered in high resolution on the upper slope).

The initial site location given the ship (HOPS20-04) reflected the location of nearby seismic crossing lines on the Astoria Fan collected during cruise RR1718, however a decision was made to occupy as close to the Y6501-E2 core location as possible vis a vis adhering to the presumably Loran-A derived coordinates included in the coring data sheet. After a short transit, during which period we collected Chirp data to inform on stratigraphic context in the complicated channelized fan depositional environment, we arrived at our target destination. We determined this would be a good lithology to trial the new

Cerakote treated barrels, as pullout tensions in glacial clay are frequently higher than those experienced in Holocene hemipelagic sediments. As the Chirp subbottom lithology was unlike the upper slope sites cored previously during the cruise, we elected to sample with the 20' Giant Gravity Corer. The first deployment, with standard galvanized barrels, recovered 4.55 m of sediment with a pullout tension of 9,115 lbs. The second deployment, with the Cerakote-treated barrels, had similar pullout tension of 8,769 lbs, however mud showed penetration ~4' higher up the core barrel. Disappointingly, however, the Cerakote core failed to recover any sediment below the first hard reflector imaged on the Chirp (a well-sorted turbidite sand at ~1.44 m). MSCL data collected shipboard did not show unequivocal evidence of IRD recovery, although Co-Chief Walczak remains relentlessly optimistic that we'll find it upon CT scanning of the cores or, in the worst case, on a future expedition.

Station 7: Basin Near DSDP Site 175/MARSSAM Engineering Test

Pre-cruise location HOPS20-01 was planned to be a reoccupation of DSDP Site 175, originally drilled in 1971 with poor overall recovery using rotary core methods. The site is located in a syncline basin on the lower slope, west of Newport, OR. Seismic lines are available in the area from Cruise GT8909, from which we have previously used the low resolution Line 044 to get a sense for the basin. Core descriptions indicate green mud with minimal sand layers to about 120 m depth and more frequent sand layers below that. Preliminary analysis by Reilly and Walczak on DSDP Site 175 samples suggest enough benthic and planktonic foraminifera for radiocarbon and stable isotope analysis. The transition to sand-poor sediments occurred close to the last occurrence or *Pseudoemiliani lacunosa* (~440 ka) and below the first occurrence of *Emiliani huxleyi* (~270 ka) calcareous nannofossils, suggesting long term accumulation rates of 10-30 cm/kyr and providing the opportunity to recover a moderate resolution distal palaeoceanographic site on the continental slope that could be compared with our other coring locations.

After the low pull-out tensions, good recovery, and promising sediments at the lower slope basin at Station 5 Core OC2006A-23JC, we rigged a 50 ft piston core before transiting to the DSDP Site 175 location, expecting similar sediments to those we cored at Core OC2006A-23JC. This was the last station planned before heading back to Newport, OR and one of our targets for the MARSSAM engineering test, comparing the performance of ceramic coated versus standard galvanized steel barrels. Due to lack of time, our goal was to take one core the evening of July 12 and the second the morning of July 13.

Upon arrival to the site we had difficulty imaging sediments beyond a few meters below the seafloor and all members present for the quick survey agreed that we should not deploy the 50 ft piston core at that location. We decided to quickly survey a few east-west trending lines in the small basin north of the DSDP Site 175 basin and found a complex sub-bottom with faulting and tectonic deformation. Pressed for time to begin coring so that the planned engineering test could be completed during this cruise, we chose a small tectonic basin within the larger basin, containing ponded sediments that we could image to below 15 m. We did not have enough time to conduct a detailed survey of the basin containing DSDP Site 175 or the larger basin to the east of this basin but think this may be a worthwhile effort in a future expedition.

The maximum pull out tension for the first core, Core OC2006A-30JC using Cerakote painted barrels, was 13,468 lbs and recovered 13.29 m of sediment, while the pull out tension for the second core, Core CO2006A-31JC using the unpainted galvanized steel barrels, was 14,223 lbs and recovered 13.34 m of sediment. The recovered sediment observed at core breaks was green, predominantly silt/clay occasionally intermixed with fine sand. Core OC2006A-30JC sections 8, 9, and 10 had voids around section breaks, which were cut out. Core OC2006A-31JC did not seem to have any voids. The sediments often expanded after cutting the section breaks, making it difficult to cap and sometimes leading to loss of some of sediment at these section breaks. Core OC2006A-30JC continued to expand after recovery and overnight. To relieve some of the pressure we cut small holes into the end caps of the sections that had bulging end caps. However, the next morning, one of the cores expanded enough to remove the end cap. Seeing the same expansion in some of the recovered sections of OC2006A-31JC as observed in the previous core OC2006A-30JC, we drilled small holes in the liners approximately along the splitting surface at ~50 cm intervals to help relieve the pressure. This seemed to be effective, with gasses and some sediment escaping from the drilled holes. We expect there to be some coring deformation associated with this pressure release.

We hypothesize that this core, if dated, could be used to study the deformation rates and tectonic activity of this basin when correlated to features that we observed using the sub-bottom profile. Accordingly, we completed a detailed CHIRP survey of the small basin overnight between coring operations to map structural and tectonic features.

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Appendixes

Appendix 1: COVID-19 Safety Information

R/V *Oceanus*

Oregon State University

Onboard COVID-19 Mitigation

Introduction:

Safety of everyone aboard the R/V Oceanus is our top priority at Oregon State University –Ship Operations. With COVID-19 concerns we have established best practices to minimize exposure while aboard and everyone’s participation is required. Please adhere to all information in this document and please speak with the crew if you have any questions.

Thanks,
Kaya Johnson
Marine Superintendent

Practice good hygiene: Wash your hands often and use sanitizer when soap and water are not available. Avoid touching your face, nose, mouth, and eyes. Cover your cough/sneeze in the crook of you elbow. Don fresh clothing daily, contain and launder soiled clothing regularly.

Practice social distancing: Avoid physical contact with others and maintain at least 6’ of space when possible.

Use PPE: We recommend the utilization of face coverings while in public areas, inside the vessel. Additional PPE, such as gloves and lab coats are also encouraged.

Galley and Mess:

At all times:

-Only galley staff are permitted in the galley.

- Use serving utensils provided.
- Wash your hands before and after handling any utensils, packaged items, containers, etc.
- When accessing mid-rats, wash your hands before and after. Do not touch food directly (use flatware or utensils).
- Avoid touching your face. Cover your cough. Maintain social distancing.

During meal times:

- Mess deck will be closed for cleaning 30 minutes prior to every meal. Please vacate the mess area during this time.
- Please occupy the mess and eat only during the time assigned to your meal group.
- No self-service. Galley personnel will plate your meal and provide utensils. Please be patient and polite.
- One person per table is recommended for appropriate social distancing.
- When returning dirty plates and flatware, do not enter galley. Please place soiled dishes in the bus tub provided.

Laundry: During this time, higher usage of the ship's laundry facilities is expected. Be sure to remove clean laundry promptly so that others are not tempted to handle your laundry. Do not leave soiled laundry in the laundry area while waiting for an available machine.

Restricted Spaces: The bridge, engineering spaces, galley, and isolation cabin will be restricted and all non-essential crew and scientists must remain clear. We also ask that you not enter any cabin not assigned to you. Use only the heads adjacent to your assigned cabin.

Sanitation: Ship's crew will clean and sanitize high touch areas of the vessel, multiple times a day. We ask that you do the same with your equipment, computers, and mobile devices whenever possible.

Screening and Monitoring: While we expect this process to evolve rapidly, it is imperative that you participate in the screening and monitoring plan developed for your cruise. Report all symptoms accurately and truthfully, do not conceal an illness. Responsible behavior is essential to protecting ourselves and each other.

Additional Information Sources:

For up to date, factual information, please see the following sources.

Center for Disease Control

<https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/index.html>

Oregon Health Authority

<https://govstatus.egov.com/OR-OHA-COVID-19>

Lincoln County Health and Human Services

<https://www.co.lincoln.or.us/hhs/page/2019-novel-coronavirus>

Oregon State University

<https://covid.oregonstate.edu/>

What will happen if someone gets sick?

As always, the safety of personnel is our primary concern. In the event that someone develops an illness, we have a response plan to assess the situation, care for the ill, and protect the healthy. The general steps are as follows:

- An ill person will be isolated and symptoms assessed under the direction of George Washington – Maritime Medical Access

- If the illness is determined (by GW-MMA) to be a suspected COVID-19 case, that person will be quarantined in a dedicated cabin. While they will be restricted to that cabin, medical treatment will continue; meals, snacks, and beverages will be delivered; we will provide as much comfort as possible.

- Anyone who has had close contact with the suspected infected individual will self-isolate and will be closely monitored.

- The cruise will be immediately terminated and arrangements made for the earliest possible port arrival.

- Required reports will be made and we will comply with any government or medical authority orders received. This may include whole vessel quarantine upon port arrival. Early illness reporting, accurate monitoring, and enthusiastic participation in the practices noted here will be the most effective way to avoid an official quarantine order.

Appendix 2: Coring Related UNOLS Cruise Planner Information

Mobilization/ Demobilization Logistics

Approximately how many heavy crane picks do you expect on mobilization day? How many total crane picks do you expect on mobilization day? Please provide a brief description of large/heavy items (i.e. multicore, moorings, mass spec).

MC400 - 2 picks JPC - 1 pick Hiab crane - 1 pick Core bucket - 1 pick Core weight - 1 pick Core pipe rack - 1 pick Core shack - 1 pick MST van - 1 pick Berthing van - 1 pick Oceanus crane crutch (if not already onboard) - 1 pick Core liner - 1 pick ? spares ? - 1 pick

The science party is welcome to stay aboard the RV Oceanus the night before leaving port. Do you plan on staying on the ship the night before the cruise starts?

Yes

RV Oceanus- Meal Expectations. The Oceanus generally does not provide meals during the Mobilization day or during the Demobilization day due to funding and extra stress on the galley staff. The first meal that we provide to the science party will be breakfast the morning that the ship leaves (if AM departure), or lunch (if afternoon departure). By clicking the box below, you acknowledge our mob/ demob meal policy.

Checked

Please alert us to any special requirements or concerns you may have regarding mobilization/demobilization.

Please let us know what pier mob/demob will occur on. The truck with our gear will likely weigh >20,000 lbs, so if we need to move things across the pier with fork lifts we will need to budget adequate time.

Shipping

Please describe in detail any equipment or instruments that you will be shipping to or from the RV Oceanus. Include dimensions, weights, storage requirements, hazmat info, and total number of packages/pallets. Add bills of lading and shipping information to the attachments section on the Cruise Planning home page.

All of our large equipment will come to ShipOps or NOAA (depending on pier assignment) via OSU flatbed or commercial trucker. We'll probably need to unload trucks and store equipment in the yard over the course of a day or two, then ferry out to the ship on the onload day. No small packages will be delivered.

I, as the chief scientist, acknowledge that I am responsible for the coordination and on-time delivery of all science-related shipments. Each package will be labeled appropriately with the cruise number and POC name/phone number.

Checked

Please alert us to any special requirements or concerns you may have regarding shipping packages, samples, or pallets.

Depending on the pier the onload may take a while due to access issues. When unloading Atlantis for piston coring from the NOAA pier everything took about twice as long as usual, due to the narrow causeway.

General Overboarding

Please provide a broad overview of the overboarding operations that are planned for your cruise. Information such as the periodicity, time of day, instrumentation, personnel required, and desired location are helpful.

The operational focus of this cruise will be jumbo piston coring (JPC), which will be performed over the starboard rail using the MARSSAM Hiab crane and the ship's trawl crane. Deployments will be directed by two MARSSAM technicians. From the ship we will need one winch and one crane operator. Pending weather etc. our goal is to conduct the majority of JPC operations during daylight hours, and we will have at least one 8 hour break in coring every day. We understand the limitations in staffing associated with our current situation and that true 24 hour operations won't be possible. In addition to JPC operations we will also be multi-coring and gravity coring. As for the JPC, MARSSAM technicians will be on hand to lead all deployments. The multi-corer used will be the MC-400, and it will be deployed through the A-frame. We will need a winch operator for multicoring operations. The large diameter gravity corer ('Big Bertha') will be deployed over the starboard rail using the MARSSAM Hiab and the Oceanus' trawl crane. Similar to JPC deployments, we will need a winch operator and a crane operator for gravity coring. We will also be collecting several plankton tows over the course of the cruise. We will populate this operation with more details in the near future.

Approximately how much does each instrument being overboarded weigh?

Jumbo Piston Corer (w/trigger core): 4200-5500 lbs (depending on how it's rigged, something assessed on a site-by-site basis) Giant Gravity Corer: 3500 - 4000 lbs (again depending on how it's rigged) MC-400: 1500 lbs Plankton net: 250 lbs (?? not sure about this; will confirm shortly)

What are the proposed depths for each overboarding operation?

Approximately ~500m - 2500m (see waypoint table for site-by-site breakdown)

Will you be conducting 24-hr deck operations?

Yes

For 24-hr deck ops, please describe the experience level of your science party/technicians. Is someone from your group comfortable with supervising the deck as needed?

The science party is highly experienced and we are sailing with 3 dedicated MARSSAM technicians to lead overboarding operations.

Do you require the use of a TSE spooler? This is common for mooring operations

No

Winches and Wires. The R/V Oceanus is outfitted with two Starboard .322" EM wire winches and a deep-sea winch capable of utilizing either a 9/16" trawl wire, .680" EM wire, or .681" fiber optic wire. Swapping wires on the deep-sea winch is done with a shore crane and requires advanced planning. All wires can be used to lower scientific instrumentation over the side. If the permanent winches and wire options listed below do not meet the specific needs, please contact the Marine Technician Superintendent to discuss other options.

I plan on using the .322" EM cable to deploy NETS or OTHER instruments off the starboard side of the ship.

On the .322" wire, do you plan on using the EM conductors?

No, I just need the mechanical termination to hang a net (no real-time data).

I plan on using the 9/16" trawl cable to deploy larger equipment

For the 9/16" trawl wire, the Oceanus can deploy instruments off the stern via the A-Frame or over the starboard side via the crane and crutch. If you have deployed equipment off of the Oceanus before, which method did you use?

I will need to deploy this instrument off the stern through the A-Frame.

I will need to deploy this instrument off the starboard side using the crane and crane crutch. *** Note: The Oceanus does not normally carry the crane crutch on board and this will need to be arranged well before your cruise.

Please alert us to any special requirements or concerns you may have regarding overboarding.

We will need to attach a feige fitting to the 9/16" and do a pull-test using either a water bag or deck plate at some point before we leave the dock. Again for much of what we want to do we'll need both a crane and a winch operator and depending on weather and sea state there may be windows when overboarding ops are intensive. We do understand the staffing limitations and will work with Brandon and Jeremy to schedule over-the-side events such that the available operators get adequate rest. Also, we've covered this but we will need Appendix A permission to pull to ~20,000 lbs. We aim to keep it under 18,000 lbs and are pretty good at that but a little upward wiggle room can save a corer. Critical to successful coring is a ship that is still in the water. For survey we request the captain run a drift line, both to collect high-res Chirp data as well as to figure out what heading would result in the greatest stability during coring. It is more important that the ship is as still as possible than that we core precisely at the targeted GPS coordinates.

Appendix 3: List of Stations and Deployments

Station	Number	Type*	Latitude (deg. min. N)	Longitude (deg. min. W)	Depth (m)	Length (m)
0	1	NT	45 14.1264'	124 28.5427'	-	-
0	1	W	45 14.0632'	124 28.4747'	-	-
1	2	GC	45 51.8781'	124 51.5203'	829	201.1
1	2	GC	45 51.8059'	124 51.4231'	836	205.5
1	4	MC	45 51.8966'	124 1.3257'	827	0.30-0.36
1	5	W				
2	6	MC	46 19.588'	124 41.931'	774	0.41-0.43
2	7	MC	46 16.7152'	124 52.4314'	839	0.38-0.41
2	8	NT	46 16.713'	124 52.4793	-	-
2	9	GC	46 16.745'	124 52.406'	841	434.7
2	10	JC (TC)	46 16.7229'	124 52.3104'	839	612.4 (243.6)
3	11	JC (TC)	47 33.8976'	125 19.2256'	899	817.4 (251.6)
3	12	JC (TC)	47 34.125'	125 19.038'	894	1117.2 (229.9)
3	13	MC	47 33.6916'	125 19.0665'	910	0.35-0.38
3	14	MC	47 27.6822'	125 9.4877	658	0.04-0.085
4	15	GC	46 48.0339'	125 4.5776'	638	357.4
4	16	JC (TC)	46 47.2197'	125 3.7751'	681	807.2 (263.4)
4	17	W	46 46.5693'	125 3.8674'	-	-
4	18	JC (TC)	46 46.4849'	125 3.7922'	731	1404.3 (206.9)
4	19	NT	46 46.1919'	125 3.8081'	-	-
4	20	MC	46 46.464'	125 3.8045'	732	0.30-0.32
4	21	W	46 38.9254'	125 4.7121'	-	-
5	22	MC	45 27.5727'	125 13.9244'	1977	0.31-0.37
5	23	JC (TC)	45 27.547'	125 14.0034'	1975	1111 (262.7)
6	24	W	45 44.1538'	125 34.8929'	-	-
6	25	GC	45 43.2209'	125 37.2239'	2210	455.1
6	26	GC	45 43.1977'	125 37.2064'	2210	143.6
1	27	JC (TC)	45 51.953'	124 51.3008'	828	1003.2 (235.4)
1	28	NT	45 51.1441'	124 51.7349'	-	-
1	29	W	45 49.4934'	124 52.4702'	-	-
7	30	JC (TC)	44 53.2159'	125 17.0814'	2103	1329.2 (229.6)
7	31	JC (TC)	44 53.2201'	125 17.0635'	2103	1334.1 (184.7)

* MC = MC 400 Multi Core; GC = Gravity Core; PC = Piston Core; TC = Trigger Core; NT = Plankton Net Tow; W = Flow Through Water Sample

Appendix 4: Multi Sensor Core Logger Summary Figures

OC2006A, Core 2GC

OC2006A, Core 3GC

OC2006A, Core 10PC, 10TC, 9GC

OC2006A, Core 11JC and 11TC

OC2006A, Core 12JC and 12TC

OC2006A, Core 15GC

OC2006A, Core 16JC and 16TC

OC2006A, Core 18JC and 18TC

OC2006A, Core 23JC and 23TC

OC2006A, Core 25GC

OC2006A, Core 26GC

OC2006A, Core 27JC and 27TC

OC2006A, Core 30JC and 30TC

OC2006A, Core 31JC and 31TC

